

TO MY AJJA, AJJI, PROF. DOREIRAJ & MADHUSUDHAN SIR, FOR INSPIRING ME TO BE A
SCIENTIST.

DECLARATION

This thesis is a presentation of my original research work. Wherever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly, with due reference to the literature, and acknowledgement of collaborative research and discussions.

The work was done under the guidance of Professor Shannon Olsson, at the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Mumbai.

[Pavan Kumar Kaushik]

In my capacity as supervisor of the candidate's thesis, I certify that the above statements are true to the best of my knowledge.

[Prof. Shannon Olsson]

Date: 18/05/2022

CERTIFICATE

I certify that this thesis entitled “**Prakruti māyé : Using Virtual Reality to deconstruct insect ecology**” comprises research work carried out by **Pavan Kumar Kaushik** at National Centre for Biological Sciences under the supervision of **Prof. Shannon Olsson** during the period Aug 2014 – Jan 2021 for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy of the Tata Institute of Fundamental Research (TIFR). The results presented in this thesis have not been submitted previously to this or any other University for a PhD or any other degree.

Head Academics
National Centre for Biological Sciences
Tata Institute of Fundamental Research
Bangalore

Listing of figures

1.1	An insect’s multisensory view of reality.	10
1.2	Birth of Virtual Reality 1.	12
2.1	First flight	20
2.2	Optomotor to toilet paper	22
2.3	Precise positioning and illumination.	23
2.4	Birth of Virtual Reality 2.	25
2.5	The pilot VR.	29
2.6	Tunable tether cloning machine.	30
2.7	Tethered fly array.	31
2.8	Stuck in a Servo Spiral	33
2.9	Hiding behind a veil.	34
2.10	Trying to make things invisible.	37
2.11	A few iterations of the Rasen shuriken.	38
3.1	MultiMoVR arena.	41
3.2	Complex visual landscape in VR.	42
3.3	Perspective calibration.	43
3.4	The Graphical User Interface.	44
3.5	Closed loop airflow input : 360° glass	45
3.6	Closed loop odour input: Toroidal suction.	46
3.7	Odour stimulus calibration	48
3.8	The <i>Rasen Shuriken</i>	50
3.9	Wing Beat Amplitude Difference.	52
3.10	Precise positioning and illumination.	53
3.11	Frugal 7 DoF imaging.	54
3.12	Impose response.	57
3.13	Finding the right gain 1.	58
3.14	Finding the right gain 2.	59
4.1	Navigating to targets: Apple fly.	65

4.2	Response of tethered insects to virtual targets.	66
4.3	Navigating to targets: Crane fly.	67
4.4	Navigating to targets: Mosquito.	68
4.5	Navigating to targets Hoverfly.	68
4.6	Measuring reactive distance in VR 2.	69
4.7	A shift in perspective.	70
4.8	Measuring reactive distance in VR 1.	70
4.9	Distinguishing distance and size using motion parallax 1.	71
4.10	Distinguishing distance and size using motion parallax 2.	72
4.11	The virtual windscape.	72
4.12	Response of apple flies to windscapes at large spatial and temporal scales 2.	73
4.13	Navigating the wind with no optic flow.	74
4.14	Invisible motion.	74
4.15	Response of apple flies to windscapes at large spatial and temporal scales 3.	75
4.16	The virtual odourscape.	76
4.17	Response of apple flies to odour flux at large spatial and temporal scales.	77

List of Tables

I.1	Recent advances in virtual reality technologies developed for studying insects . . .	15
A.1	Glossary of keywords	89
A.3	Bill of materials	90